

Appendix A

Table A.1: Description of nodes in the Bayesian Network, their states, and methods use to quantify their conditional probabilities.

Node	Description	States	CPT method	Source
Input nodes - remote sensing				
Land cover classification	Classification	Evergreen forest, deciduous forest, non-forest	Confusion matrix	Random forest classification with combination of LiDAR, aerial CIR images and Sentinel2
Crown cover (measured)	Measured cover of vegetation above 3 m	10 states: 0 - 100 [%]	Normal distribution around actual state	LiDAR (Lastools (Isenburg 2016)), error estimated based on Moeser et al. 2014
Roughness (measured)	Measured terrain roughness	9 states: 0 - 1	Fuzzy definition of categories based on ground truth	Derived from LiDAR-based DTM (Sappington et al. 2007)
Gap width (measured)	Width (along contour lines) of non-forested area [m]	9 states: 0 - 8000 [m]	Normal distribution around actual state	Derived from LiDAR-based CHM
Building (detected)	Presence of a building detected	Boolean	Confusion matrix	Building extraction from LiDAR (Lastools)
Curvature	Planar slope curvature	7 states: -45 - 5		Derived from LiDAR-based DTM
Slope	Slope angle	8 states: 0 - 90 [°]		From LiDAR-based DTM
Elevation	Elevation [m a.s.l.]	7 states: 1500 - 2900		Derived from LiDAR-based DTM
Input nodes - avalanche hazard data				
Max new snow height	Annual maximum new snow height, which determines the avalanche release scenario	9 states: 0 - 2 [m]	Gumbel distribution of maximum new snow height, Davos, Fluelastrasse	(Salm et al. 1990, SLF 2017)
Velocity 300	Maximum velocity under the 300 year scenario	9 states: 0 - 60 [m/s]		RAMMS (Christen et al. 2010) model output
Velocity 30	Maximum velocity under the 30 year scenario	10 states: 0 - 60 [m/s]		RAMMS model output

Nodes representing ecosystem structure

Crown cover	Cover of vegetation above 3 m	10 states: 0 - 100 [%]	Fuzzy logic definition of categories	
Crown cover (class)	Category of forest density	Dense, scattered, open, non-forest		
Roughness (class)	Category of terrain roughness	Rough, knobby, smooth		
Land cover	Actual land cover class	Evergreen forest, deciduous forest, non-forest	Based on ground truth plots	
Gap width	Width (along contour lines) of non-forested area [m]	9 states: 0 - 8000 [m]		
Potential release prevention	Potential of forest to prevent an avalanche release	Boolean	Logistic model	(Bebi et al. 2001)
Potential detrainment	Capacity of forest to remove snow from avalanche flow	12 states: 0 - 120 [Pa]	Expert knowledge (four-point estimation)	(Feistl et al. 2014, Teich et al. 2014)

Nodes representing the hazard process

Release	Probability of an avalanche release	Boolean	Fuzzy logic	(Veitinger et al. 2016)
Release height	Height of snow released in the event of an avalanche	10 states: 0 - 3 [m]	Logical combination of "Release" and "Max new snow height", corrected for "Slope"	(Salm et al. 1990)
Velocity	Maximum avalanche flow velocity	9 states: 0 - 60 [m/s]	Defined by scenarios, with uncertainty estimated based on simulations with varying input parameters	RAMMS (Christen et al. 2010)
Max pressure	Maximum avalanche pressure	4 states: = 0 - 300 [kPa]	Derived from velocity, with uncertainty estimated based on simulations with varying input parameters	RAMMS

Nodes representing ecosystem functions

Release prevented	Probability a release would	Boolean	Logical combination of "Release" and
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	be prevented by the forest		"Potential prevention"	
Prevention	Height of snow in prevented avalanche release	11 states: 0 - 3 [m]	Logical combination of "Release prevented" and "Release height"	
Detrainment	Height of snow detrainment in forest during avalanche	7 states: 0 - 0.8 [m]	Learning from simulations with varying input parameters	RAMMS

Risk assessment and valuation nodes

Building	Presence of a building	Boolean		
Building type	Type of building	One-family house, farm building, guesthouse, multi-family house, industrial, infrastructure	Distribution of types from local data	Communal cadaster (Davos, unpublished)
Lethality	Avalanche pressure is lethal	Boolean	Fuzzy logic based on values from literature	Swiss National Platform for Natural Hazards (Planat 2008, BAFU 2015)
People per building	Average no. of people per building	6 states: 0 - 20	Fuzzy logic based on values from literature	Swiss National Platform for Natural Hazards
People present	People are present in a building	Boolean	Fuzzy logic based on values from literature	Swiss National Platform for Natural Hazards
Damage	Building is destroyed by avalanche	Boolean	Fuzzy logic based on values from literature	Swiss National Platform for Natural Hazards
Building cost	Cost of destroyed building	6 states: 0 - 10 ⁷ [CHF]	Distribution per type from local data	Communal cadaster (Davos, unpublished)
Damage (cost)	Cost due to damaged building	7 states: 0 - 10 ⁷ [CHF]	Logical combination of "Damage" and "Building cost"	
Cost of human death		Constant: 5*10 ⁶ [CHF]	Constant value from literature	Life Quality Index approach (Merz et al. 1995)
Lortality (cost)		5 states: 0 - 10 ⁸ [CHF]	Logical combination of "Lethality" and "Cost of human death"	

Output nodes

Provision	Combination of prevented release and	12 states: 0 - 4 [m]	Sum of "Prevention" and "Detrainment"	
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detrained snow
height

Demand	Avalanche risk to people and buildings	5 states: 0 - $1.1 \cdot 10^8$ [CHF]	Sum of "Damage (cost)" and "Lethality (cost)"
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Appendix B: Demand for avalanche protection

Figure B.1: Map of modelled demand for avalanche protection in the Dischma valley, Davos, Switzerland. Areas with high values correspond to buildings, and the higher values are mostly associated with higher uncertainties (dark red).

Figure B.2: Sankey diagram of stepwise sensitivity analysis of the BN for avalanche protection demand.

Appendix C: Examples of posterior probability distributions and posterior sensitivities

Figure C.1: Example of posterior probability distribution of avalanche protection provision.

Figure C.2: Stepwise sensitivity analysis for posterior distribution of avalanche protection provision (Figure C.1). Node colours show the uncertainty (entropy) of the nodes, while the links are coloured according to the method used to quantify them.

Figure C.3: Example of posterior probability distribution of avalanche protection demand.

Figure C.4: Stepwise sensitivity analysis for posterior distribution of avalanche protection demand (Figure C.3). Node colours show the uncertainty (entropy) of the nodes, while the links are coloured according to the method used to quantify them.